

GOOD TEACHER-BEST MOTIVATOR

Amirkulova Dilnoza Zokir qizi

The 2nd course of Master's degree, SamSIFL

<https://www.doi.org/10.37547/ejsspc-v03-i02-p1-33>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 05th February 2023

Accepted: 15th February 2023

Online: 16th February 2023

KEY WORDS

Good teacher, pupils, diversity, students, lesson, schools, resources, daily routine, negative and positive behavior, best teacher's rules, problems, tight transitions, entry routine, seat signals, authoritarian teaching style, authoritarian teaching, permissive teaching, indulgent teachers.

ABSTRACT

In this article, we will look through what main features of good teachers, the main features of this and why we need classroom management. Every teacher should use classroom management in her/his lesson. But some of them cannot know its facilities. This article is explained clearly and shortly about what features need teachers.

One of the most famous and best teacher's quotes says **"Teaching is the one profession that creates all other professions."**

It is an undeniable fact that, without good teachers, there would be no scientists, politicians, engineers, doctors, writers, or artists. Teachers are the foundation of a **good education system**. When we talk about the role of a teacher in the learning process; it is not just in academics or sports, but also in the school of life.

What makes a Good Teacher?

A teacher is not just someone who teaches lessons and subjects. A teacher can be a person who teaches morality, character building, art, sport, a belief, a faith, or even a way of living.

He/ She is a guide, mentor, philosopher, and friend. A teacher guides the **student** to explore his/her talents and become successful in life.

There are teachers in the world who just teach the subject and there are visionaries who have motivated hundreds and thousands of **students**. In this blog, we will learn more about **15 best teachers in the world ever**.

These great teachers stand apart from the thousands of other teachers across the globe for their passion and commitment to **teaching**. Their lives show us the **multiple roles of teachers** in a **student's** life. These teachers didn't confine **teaching** to the four walls of a classroom. They showed a world of opportunities to their **students**.

Teachers often play an important part in our lives even when we don't realise it. A [good teacher](#) is someone who helps us become a good human being first and later on, a good citizen. Different countries celebrate teacher's day on different dates to mark the contribution of the teachers to their society. All teachers play a significant role in shaping a student's life during their formative years. With their patience and love, they leave a huge impact on a student's life. Let's discuss some of the **Best Teachers in the World!** When you think of your favourite teacher, which one comes to your mind? The math teacher that helped you solve problems on fractions, trigonometry, etc., or your [sports](#) teacher who helped you discover a new sport or the one who was the reason behind your current career path? While some teachers have changed lives, some have changed the world with their extraordinary talent and knowledge. Let's see how these 7 teachers changed the world.

Sir Isaac Newton was a famous teacher, mathematician, and physicist who established the theory of gravity. He applied his theories of the Law of Motion and gravity to explain the motion of the Sun and planets. He was the first to discover that white light is made up of a spectrum of colours. The 'Principia' was a result of Newton's research which was first published in 1687 and established the foundation for classical mechanics. That book changed the way people perceived the world till then and it still continues to be the keystone of non-relativistic technologies in the world. He is surely one the **Best Teachers In The World!**

Pythagoras

Pythagoras was a philosopher, mathematician, and teacher whose theories are still taught in schools today. Known for his Pythagoras theorem of right-angled triangles, he is known as the "father of numbers" and also invented the relationship between math and music. In Croton, he established a secret society where the people followed a structured life.

Dr. Sarvepalli Radhakrishnan

The man whose birthday, 5th September, is celebrated as Teacher's Day in India every year was the first Vice President and the second President of India. He defended Hinduism from "uninformed Western criticism" and contributed to the formation of contemporary Hindu identity. He played an influential role in the understanding of Hinduism in India and the

West and simultaneously earned respect in both the places. He is well known for his commentaries on Bhagavad Gita, Upanishads, and Brahma Sutra. He was honoured with the Bharat Ratna (highest civilian award in India) in 1954.

Albert Einstein

Albert Einstein, a theoretical physicist, author and a teacher was known for his contributions to the field of general and special relativity. He was also known for his mass-energy equation which was dubbed as the “most famous equation” that gave birth to the atom bomb. His work on the general theory of relativity was published in 1915 and is still regarded as the most significant concept that was developed in modern-day physics. He was rewarded the Nobel Prize in Physics in 1921 due to his outstanding work. He is surely one the **Best Teachers In The World.**

Aristotle

He was a famous Greek philosopher and scientist and is considered as “Father of Western Philosophy”. In 335 B.C., he founded his own school in Athens where he spent most of his life teaching and writing. His passion for nature, logic, and reasons led him to make contributions which are reflected in modern math, physics, biology, politics and more. He classified animals in his book; History of Animals and used the traits that are similar among animals to classify them into certain similar groups. He is also known as the Father of Zoology, where he classified the living organisms. He contributed in the fields of physics, psychology, meteorology, ethics, politics, poetics, and the list goes on! Even after 2300 years, his contributions are influential in this time and age!

John Adams

John Adams was the second president of the United States. He became a teacher in Worcester and then for a year he decided to study law. After becoming a lawyer, he assisted in the drafting of the Constitution and the Declaration of Independence. Being one of the negotiators, he was responsible for the peace treaty with Great Britain that signalled the end of the Revolutionary War. He is surely one the Best Teachers In The World.

Savitribai Phule

The first woman teacher in the country, a leading social reformer of her time, she is known for her contribution in the field of education and also standing for women's rights during the British rule in India. She built 18 schools and encouraged women education. She also worked towards preventing female infanticide, the killing of widows, and all the causes that undermined the existence of women. She was the only woman leader of the 19th century and transformed many lives due to her revolutionary work. She is surely one the **Best Teachers In The World**.

All these 7 teachers have made remarkable contributions to the world and their work still lives within us in some way or the other and marks our existence. As it is always said, an outstanding teacher always inspires us throughout our lives. These 7 teachers have definitely left a mark on our minds, hearts and the world at large!

Some characteristics of having good teacher-student relationships in the classroom involves the appropriate levels of dominance, cooperation, professionalism, and awareness of high-needs students. Dominance is defined as the teacher's ability to give clear purpose and guidance concerning student behavior and their academics. By creating clear expectations and consequences for student behavior, this builds effective relationships. Such expectations may cover classroom etiquette and behavior, group work, seating arrangements, the use of equipment and materials, and also classroom disruptions. These expectations should always be enforced with consistency among all students within the class.^[8] Inconsistency is viewed by students as unfair and will result in the students having less respect for the teacher. Assertive teacher behavior also reassures those thoughts and messages are being passed on to the student in an effective way. Assertive behavior can be achieved by using erect posture, appropriate tone of voice depending on the current situation, and taking care not to ignore inappropriate behavior by taking action.^[9] Another great strategy to build a good teacher-student relationship is using inclusive pronouns. For example, if a class is misbehaving and are getting off track, instead of saying "you need to get back to work" a teacher may say "we've got a lot of work to do today, so let's get back to it." Another technique to establishing good teacher-student relationships is William Purkey's "three pluses and a wish." These pluses are complimenting that the teacher gives to the student before making a request. The pluses help the student get into a mindset that is more likely to cooperate with the teacher. An example might look like this: "Thanks so much for your participation in class today. I love hearing your comments. I think you provided a fair amount of educational insight to the discussion. I would appreciate if you could raise your hand before commenting, so that other students can follow your example."

What makes a great teacher? Teaching is one of the most complicated jobs today. It demands broad knowledge of subject matter, curriculum, and standards; enthusiasm, a caring attitude, and a love of learning; knowledge of discipline and classroom management techniques; and a desire to make a difference in the lives of young people. With all these qualities required, it's no wonder that it's hard to find great teachers.

Here are some characteristics of great teachers

- **Great teachers set high expectations for all students.** They expect that all students can and will achieve in their classroom, and they don't give up on underachievers.

- **Great teachers have clear, written-out objectives.** Effective teachers have lesson plans that give students a clear idea of what they will be learning, what the assignments are and what the grading policy is. Assignments have learning goals and give students ample opportunity to practice new skills. The teacher is consistent in grading and returns work in a timely manner.
- **Great teachers are prepared and organized.** They are in their classrooms early and ready to teach. They present lessons in a clear and structured way. Their classrooms are organized in such a way as to minimize distractions.
- **Great teachers engage students and get them to look at issues in a variety of ways.** Effective teachers use facts as a starting point, not an end point; they ask “why” questions, look at all sides and encourage students to predict what will happen next. They ask questions frequently to make sure students are following along. They try to engage the whole class, and they don’t allow a few students to dominate the class. They keep students motivated with varied, lively approaches.
- **Great teachers form strong relationships with their students and show that they care about them as people.** Great teachers are warm, accessible, enthusiastic and caring. Teachers with these qualities are known to stay after school and make themselves available to students and parents who need them. They are involved in school-wide committees and activities, and they demonstrate a commitment to the school.
- **Great teachers are masters of their subject matter.** They exhibit expertise in the subjects they are teaching and spend time continuing to gain new knowledge in their field. They present material in an enthusiastic manner and instill a hunger in their students to learn more on their own.
- **Great teachers communicate frequently with parents.** They reach parents through conferences and frequent written reports home. They don’t hesitate to pick up the telephone to call a parent if they are concerned about a student.

What No Child Left Behind means for teacher quality

The role of the teacher became an even more significant factor in education with the passage of The No Child Left Behind law in 2002.

Under the law, elementary school teachers must have a bachelor’s degree and pass a rigorous test in core curriculum areas. Middle and high school teachers must demonstrate competency in the subject area they teach by passing a test or by completing an academic major, graduate degree or comparable course work. These requirements already apply to all new hires.

Schools are required to tell parents about the qualifications of all teachers, and they must notify parents if their child is taught for more than four weeks by a teacher who is not highly qualified. Schools that do not comply risk losing federal funding.

Although the law required states to have highly qualified teachers in every core academic classroom by the end of the 2005-2006 school year, not a single state met that deadline.

How parents can advocate for qualified teachers

Over the next decade, schools in the United States will be faced with the daunting task of hiring 2 million teachers. We know that high-quality teachers make all the difference in the

classroom. We also know that it is becoming increasingly difficult to find them and keep them. Twenty percent of new teachers leave the classroom after four years, and many teachers will be retiring in the next 15 to 20 years.

- Raise professional standards for teachers.
- Improve salaries and working conditions.
- Reinvent teacher preparation and professional development.
- Encourage and reward teacher knowledge and skills.

Implementing these recommendations, however, is a slow process, dependent upon legislation as well as increased funding from both the federal and state governments, and a will to implement changes at the school district level. Parents can work together to keep the superintendent, their school board members and their state legislators focused on the goal of having a high-quality teacher in every classroom.

Conclusion

It's important to note that no teacher will constantly fit into just one category. Students are all unique, and different situations call for different practices. However, researchers have determined that the closer a teacher is to an authoritative approach, the greater the impact they'll have on their students. Classroom management is the most important aspect of a successful classroom, but finding the right balance of control and involvement takes some trial-and-error.

If you're a new teacher, take your time to figure out what works best for you. Try different classroom management strategies and see how they impact your students. Then, ask yourself if the strategy impacts student outcomes positively or negatively. Once you have answered that question, pivot your approach as needed until you find the right balance.

On the other hand, if you are a more experienced teacher, be sure to take the time to reflect on your classroom management style and adjust it as needed. Many teachers don't intentionally choose to be permissive or indulgent, but rather their decisions lead them to lose control of their classroom. Don't let yourself get stuck in your ways with the wrong approach. It's never too late to change your teaching style to better serve your students!

References:

1. Give Kids Good Schools, International Organization, USA
2. Resolving Conflict With Your Child's Teacher, USA, 2000
3. National Board for Professional Teaching Standards, 2001
4. McEwan, Elaine K., *10 Traits of Highly Successful Schools*, Waterbrook Press, 1999
5. Bennett, William J., *The Educated Child*, Simon & Schuster, 1999
6. Intrator, Sam M., *Stories of the Courage to Teach*, Jossey-Bass, 2002